

Effect of Temperature on Intrinsic Viscosity of Partially Hydrolysed Polyacrylamide

NIMAI CHANDRA DEY

Saldiha College, Saldiha, Bankura

Manuscript received 27 February 1984, accepted 21 July 1984

Two partially hydrolysed polyacrylamides, Pusher 500 and Pusher 700 have been studied. These high molecular weight water-soluble polymers show pronounced change in rheological properties under the varying conditions of electrolyte concentrations. Intrinsic viscosity of the polymers decreases with increase of electrolyte concentrations and shows the linear relationship with reciprocal of temperature.

However, higher molecular weight and lower degree of hydrolysed polyacrylamide, Pusher 700 shows more dramatic effect than Pusher 500, which is attributed to the change in molecular size of the polymers in solution.

PARTIALLY hydrolysed polyacrylamides are recently extensively used as additives in water-flood for enhanced recovery of crude¹. In other fields also, these water-soluble and high molecular weight polymers are receiving wide applications. Most of these applications are related to the rheology and molecular size of the polymers.

In order to understand the property, the effects of temperature changes on the intrinsic viscosity of dilute solutions of the partially hydrolysed polyacrylamides have been studied. Mandelkern and Flory² have considered the temperature dependence of intrinsic viscosities of cellulose tributyrate and tricaprilate, and Flory *et al.*³ that of intrinsic viscosities of cellulose acetates and cellulose trinitrate in terms of current hydrodynamic and thermodynamic theories of polymer solutions which relate viscosity and chain configuration. The large negative temperature coefficients observed were ascribed to increases in chain flexibility. Other approaches to the problem have also been made. Manley⁴ interpreted changes in intrinsic viscosities of ethyl hydroethyl cellulose fractions with temperature in terms of varying degree of hydration. Howlett *et al.*⁵ reported a linear relationship between the logarithm of the relative viscosity and reciprocal of absolute temperature for dilute solutions of secondary cellulose acetate. In this paper, the temperature dependence of intrinsic viscosities has been discussed briefly in terms of current hydrodynamic and thermodynamic theories.

Experimental

Pusher 500 and Pusher 700 (Dow Chemical, U.S.A.), the high molecular weight water-soluble partially hydrolysed polyacrylamides, were used in the study. Their molecular characteristics were determined by viscosity method⁶ and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MOLECULAR CHARACTERISTICS OF PUSHER 500 AND PUSHER 700

Polymer	Molecular weight** × 10 ⁴	Degree of hydrolysis† %	Calculated extended polymer chain length*, μ
Pusher 500	3-4 (n=490)	37 (a=63, c=37)	12.25
Pusher 700	4.5-5.5 (n=701)	31 (a=69, c=31)	17.5

* Length of one mer unit $\text{OH}_2 - \text{CH CONH}_2$ or $\text{CH}_2 - \text{CH.COOH}$ taken as 2.5 Å.

** n = 100 times repeating unit of monomer.

† a = Amide monomer unit %, c = carboxyl monomer unit %.

Solutions of dry polymer were prepared by adding them slowly to NaCl solutions. The solution was stirred with magnetic stirrer at a low speed and kept overnight to ensure complete hydration. A 0.5 ml formaldehyde (37%) was added to 1 dm³ of the solution to prevent bacterial and oxidative degradation, if any. Viscosities of the solvent and polymer solution in the concentration range of 100 to 900 ppm were measured at several temperatures in the range of 30 to 60°. Capillary viscometers used were of such dimensions as to eliminate shear effects⁷. Measurements were made in thermostatically controlled water-bath maintained to $\pm 0.02^\circ$. All solutions were filtered before use.

Results and Discussion

Partially hydrolysed polyacrylamides are long chain high molecular weight linear polymers and made up of acrylamide and acrylic acid monomer units. The structure of the polymer reveals that due to presence of negative groups, *viz.* carboxylates the polymer chain is extended by electrostatic repulsion and the polymer as a whole changes from nearly spherical to elongated form⁸.

Intrinsic viscosities of dilute solutions of Pusher 500 and Pusher 700 at different temperatures and salinities are given in Table 2 obtained from the extrapolation of the plot of reduced viscosity vs polymer concentration. The intrinsic viscosities are also plotted against $1/T$ for Pusher 500 and Pusher 700 at three saline concentrations and the plots are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Plot of intrinsic viscosity vs $1/T$ for Pusher 500 and Pusher 700 at three saline concentrations.

TABLE 2—INTRINSIC VISCOSITIES OF PUSHER 500 AND PUSHER 700 AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND SALINITIES

Temp. K	Pusher 500			Pusher 700		
	1% brine	2% brine	3% brine	1% brine	2% brine	3% brine
303	11.24	10.04	10.01	22.01	17.71	16.34
308	11.14	10.00	9.21	21.95	17.47	16.27
313	11.15	9.89	9.15	21.09	17.34	16.23
318	10.85	9.78	9.10	20.32	17.82	16.60
323	10.60	9.30	8.92	19.21	17.20	16.96
328	10.53	10.58	10.67	20.38	17.30	17.99
333	10.31	9.12	9.01	19.24	16.22	16.08

The temperature dependence of intrinsic viscosity, $[\mu]$ follows the equation⁷

$$[\mu] = K_e M/RT - K_a M^\alpha \quad (1)$$

where, M = molecular weight of the polymer ; R = universal gas constant ; K_e , K_a and α = constants ; T = absolute temperature. Our experimental data obeys the above equation as shown in Fig. 1. This

indicates that $[\mu]$ is a linear function of $1/T$ for high molecular weight polymers also.

Intrinsic viscosity of the polymer is related to the molecular size of the polymer⁸

$$\sqrt{r^2} = 8(M[\mu])^{1/3} \quad (2)$$

$\sqrt{r^2}$, the root mean square end-to-end distance of the polymer chain (often called polymer molecular diameter) is a function of intrinsic viscosity of the polymer solutions. Plots of $[\mu]$ vs $1/T$ shows that intrinsic viscosity decreases with temperature except for Pusher 700 in 3% brine solution. This dependence is directly connected with the temperature coefficient of the thermodynamic affinity of the solvent for the polymer. If thermodynamic affinity improves as temperature rises, the coil swells more and $[\mu]$ increases with an elevation of temperature, the opposite effect is played if the affinity diminishes with the temperature rise^{9,10}.

The polymers under study contains both amide and carboxyl groups in their chain which are highly polar in character. The water molecules in the solvent are attached to the polymer by dipole-dipole attraction and the hydrogen bonding through nitrogen-oxygen and oxygen-oxygen atoms⁹. As the temperature rises, the attachment of the solvent molecules decreases and the polymer molecules suffer a decrease in solvent affinity, and so the intrinsic viscosity decreases with temperature. The electrostatic repulsion which is the cause of polymer chain extension is screened at least partially by the presence of electrolyte. As a result of which the extension of the chain is effected.

For both the polymers at all the temperatures, the intrinsic viscosity is found dramatically lower with the increase of electrolyte concentration in the polymer solution. It is evident (Fig. 1) that molecular size (which is proportional to $[\mu]$) surprisingly decreases with the higher electrolyte content. The saline effect is more predominant in Pusher 700 than in Pusher 500. The effect is so pronounced that at 3% brine concentration, the polymer chain is so contracted that $[\mu]$ increases with temperature. At this condition, the thermodynamic affinity actually improves with the rise of temperature.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Dow Chemical Company, U.S.A. for their keen interest in the research programme, and to U.G.C., New Delhi for the sanction of the project.

References

1. N. C. DEY, Ph.D. Thesis, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad, 1980.
2. L. MANDELKERN and P. J. FLORY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 2517.
3. P. J. FLORY, O. K. SPURR and D. K. CARPENTER, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1958, **27**, 231.
4. R. ST. J. MANLEY, *Arkiv Kemi*, 1956, **9**, 519.

5. F. HOWLETT, E. MINSHALL and A. R. URQUHART, *J. Text. Inst.*, 1944, 35, T133.
6. P. J. FLORY, "Principles of Polymer Chemistry", Cornell Univ. Press, Ithaca, 1953, Chap. 14.
7. W. R. MOORE in "Progress in Polymer Science", ed. A. D. JENKIN, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1967, Vol. I, p. 27.
8. N. C. DEY and A. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Hung. J. Ind. Chem.*, 1980, 8, 315.
9. J. NIZETTE, N. HADJICHRISTIDIS and V. DESREUX, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 1977, 13, 41.
10. F. W. BILLMEYER, JR., "Text Book of Polymer Chemistry", John Wiley, New York, 1971, p. 84.